

Effect of Temperature on the Limiting Apparent Molal Volume ϕ° of Tetraalkylammonium Iodides in Protic and Aprotic Solvents

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The apparent molal volumes of six tetraalkylammonium iodides, namely Et_4NI to Hep_4NI , have been determined in some nonhydrogen bonded solvents namely DMF, DMSO, ethylene carbonate and propylene carbonate as well as in hydrogen bonded solvents like formamide, NMA, NMP at different temperatures and concentrations by our group, from which limiting apparent molal volumes, ϕ° , have been obtained in the usual manner. A comparative study of the results indicate that ϕ° goes on increasing with the rise in temperature both in hydrogen and nonhydrogen bonded solvents mentioned above, although $d\phi^{\circ}/dt$ decreases appreciably with the rise in temperature for salts containing smaller ions in both groups of solvents. This $d\phi^{\circ}/dt$ remains almost constant for the salts containing larger R_4N^+ ions like Hex_4N^+ and Hep_4N^+ in the second group of solvents while it decreases significantly in the first group of solvents. An attempt has been made to explain these results from the point of view of electrostatic solvation, electrostriction, relative volume effect and hydrogen bonding effect in the present communication.

THE variation of limiting apparent molal volume, ϕ° , of electrolytes with temperature has been employed to study ion-solvent interaction by many workers¹⁻⁵ both in aqueous and nonaqueous solutions, probably it is the simplest thermodynamic property to measure. Recently the electrolytes having a symmetrical large ion as tetraalkylammonium salts attracted the attention of many workers due to their large size compared with that of common ions. Attempts were made to study R_4N^+ -solvent interaction from apparent molal volume data in aqueous and nonaqueous solutions. In aqueous solution, the variation of ϕ° with temperature is mainly governed by hydrophobic ion-solvent interaction, while this type of interaction appears to be difficult in nonaqueous solvents because of similar nature of R_4N^+ ions and solvent molecules. The variation of ϕ° with temperature in nonaqueous solvents is generally explained on the basis of weakening of ion-dipole interaction and opening up of the coiled up alkyl chains at higher temperatures as well as the release of solvent molecules which may be lodged inside the R_4N^+ ions. To have a more general idea about the behaviour of R_4N^+ ions in nonaqueous solvents, it seems worthwhile to compare the results of DMF, DMSO, ethylene carbonate and propylene carbonate with those in formamide, NMA and NMP, in which sufficient data are now available. The solvents of the first group have varying dielectric constant with no hydrogen bonding while the second group have high dielectric constant along with strong hydrogen bonding.

In the present communication, an attempt has been made to deal with the nature of ion-solvent interaction of some R_4NI salts in nonaqueous

solutions to see the effect of dielectric constant, temperature and hydrogen bonding on limiting apparent molal volume.

Results and Discussion

The ϕ° values for R_4NI salts in different solvents at different temperatures are given in Tables 1 and 2. These values have been plotted against temperature and the ϕ° vs. t curves are given in figures 1 to 4. Keeping in mind the space, only two sets of graphs for two salts namely Pr_4NI and Hep_4NI are given. It may be noted from figures that in both groups of solvents limiting apparent molal volume, ϕ° , goes on increasing with the rise in temperature for almost all tetraalkylammonium iodides used, although $d\phi^{\circ}/dt$ decreases. However, this decrease of $d\phi^{\circ}/dt$ appears to be sharp in the first group of solvents as compared to the solvents of second group; indicating some ion-solvent interaction but somewhat stronger in the first group of solvents than in the solvents of the second group. It may be recalled that for larger R_4N^+ ions, $d\phi^{\circ}/dt$ is almost a constant in the solvents of the second group suggesting that some special kind of ion-solvent interaction is present in such cases. It may be due to the release of solvent molecules loosely bonded to the R_4N^+ ions and of the solvent molecules which may be accommodated inside the larger R_4N^+ ions and are held there by weak van der Waals forces but come out at higher temperatures; besides the long alkyl chains may remain coiled up at lower temperatures and may open up slowly at higher temperatures. The same should be true in the solvents of the first group as well and so the observed significant decrease in the $d\phi^{\circ}/dt$ values for larger R_4N^+ ions in these solvents at higher

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TABLE 1— ϕ° OF R_4NI SALTS IN SOME NONHYDROGEN BONDED SOLVENTS

Solvent	Temp. C°	ϕ° in ml/mole for					
		Et ₄ NI	Pr ₄ NI	Bu ₄ NI	Pen ₄ NI	Hex ₄ NI	Hep ₄ NI
DMF ($\epsilon_{35}^\circ = 36.7$)	35	166.1	238.8	307.6	377.9	449.1	515.1
	40	167.0	240.0	308.9	379.0	450.7	516.6
	50	168.6	241.6	311.0	381.6	453.0	520.1
	60	170.1	243.5	313.6	384.6	455.6	523.9
	70	171.9	245.0	315.6	387.0	457.9	527.5
DMSO ($\epsilon_{35}^\circ = 46.6$)	35	172.7	242.2	309.2	378.5	—	519.4
	40	173.3	243.6	311.0	383.3	—	521.3
	50	174.7	246.1	314.1	386.0	—	525.8
	60	175.1	247.2	315.3	387.6	—	528.0
	70	174.4	248.1	316.0	—	—	531.1
Propylene carbonate ($\epsilon_{25}^\circ = 64.7$)	35	175.6	247.3	317.2	386.1	—	522.4
	40	176.5	248.2	318.0	387.7	—	524.4
	50	177.8	249.6	321.0	390.4	—	528.2
	60	178.2	250.5	322.4	392.6	—	531.6
	70	178.8	251.1	328.8	394.8	—	535.0
Ethylene carbonate ($\epsilon_{25}^\circ = 95.3$)	35	—	—	—	—	—	—
	40	183.9	254.5	323.6	392.6	461.4	530.6
	50	186.4	257.3	326.7	396.8	464.5	534.3
	60	187.8	259.2	328.6	399.6	467.3	538.4
	70	188.5	260.6	330.2	401.3	470.8	542.1

TABLE 2— ϕ° OF R_4NI SALTS IN SOME HYDROGEN BONDED SOLVENTS

Solvent	Temp. C°	ϕ° in ml/mole for					
		Et ₄ NI	Pr ₄ NI	Bu ₄ NI	Pen ₄ NI	Hex ₄ NI	Hep ₄ NI
Formamide ($\epsilon_{25}^\circ = 109.5$)	35	186.6	258.4	325.8	398.5	463.6	—
	40	187.1	259.4	327.2	400.5	465.4	—
	50	187.6	261.0	329.2	402.2	468.6	—
	60	188.1	262.2	331.0	403.6	472.1	—
	70	188.5	263.2	333.1	404.6	475.0	—
NMP ($\epsilon_{25}^\circ = 176$)	35	—	211.7	319.2	391.8	—	524.6
	40	—	212.7	320.2	393.8	—	526.6
	50	—	214.5	322.6	396.8	—	528.5
	60	—	216.5	325.0	399.7	—	531.0
	70	—	217.8	327.0	402.8	—	533.5
NMA ($\epsilon_{25}^\circ = 185$)	35	175.4	247.5	322.9	391.1	461.2	527.3
	40	177.1	249.2	324.6	393.4	463.1	530.0
	50	179.9	252.5	327.0	397.8	466.4	535.4
	60	181.9	254.8	329.0	402.1	468.7	539.4
	70	182.8	256.0	330.6	406.2	471.1	543.5

temperatures remain unexplained at this stage. But, it may be due to the absence of buffering action of the hydrogen bonding, some other factors also appear to play an important role in controlling the general variation of ϕ° with temperature in different solvents.

A close look into the two groups of solvents suggests a solution to this riddle. While solvents of the first group are more or less nonhydrogen bonded, solvents of the second group are strongly hydrogen bonded. The ion-solvent dipole interaction energy in the first group of solvents in absence of any appreciable hydrogen bond energy, would be appreciable and the attachment of solvent molecules even to the R_4N^+ ions may not be loose; at the same time no structure formation would occur in the solvents

around the ions⁶. On the other hand in the solvents of the second group, a similar ion-solvent dipole interaction energy will lead to the breaking of strong intermolecular hydrogen bonds and loosening up of the solvent structure around the ions, so that the attachment of the solvent molecules to the R_4N^+ ions should be weaker. The net result will be weaker solvation*. Now in the solvents of the first group, some solvent molecules would be associated with R_4N^+ ions while outside the ion sphere, the solvent structure would be almost the same as in the pure solvent, so the expansion of the solution on heating

* The situation would be different for small common ions with high surface charge density which would lead to strong ion-solvent interaction together with primary and secondary solvation depending upon the radius of the ion concerned.

Fig. 1. The temperature dependence of ϕ° of Pr_4NI in some non-hydrogen bonded solvents.

would be comparatively less than that of the pure solvent, and $d\phi^\circ/dt$ would decrease with the rise in temperature. In solvents of the second group, due to the comparatively weaker solvation in presence of larger R_4N^+ ions on account of the low surface charge density, the solution may expand more rapidly than the pure solvent and $d\phi^\circ/dt$ remain almost a constant (if the R_4N^+ ions are not too small like Me_4N^+ , Et_4N^+ and Pr_4N^+). However, there appears to be the probability of some penetration of space in between partially coiled up four alkyl chains attached to the central nitrogen atom by the solvent molecules. But this penetration will be less due to higher thermal energy at higher temperatures and so $d\phi^\circ/dt$ would remain almost constant. Thus the variation of ϕ° with temperature in solvents of the first group appears to be satisfactorily explained by the concept of the ion-solvent interaction and solvation alone without invoking the idea of release of solvent molecules locked inside the larger R_4N^+ ions or of the uncoiling of the coiled up larger R-chains^{7,8} of the R_4N^+ ions at the higher temperatures.

Along with the above discussion it would be very interesting to consider the electrostriction i.e., contraction of solvent molecules in presence of electrolyte by comparing the limiting apparent molal volume in solvents of different dielectric constant as is done in Tables 1 and 2. It may be noted from Tables 1 and 2 that inspite of some exceptions, an increasing trend in the ϕ° values with increase in dielectric constant is very much noticeable. Hence it appears that the electrostriction effect would be smaller and ϕ° (salt) larger the higher the dielectric constant. This, of course one would expect as a high dielectric constant would lower the electrostatic attraction of the ions on the solvent molecules resulting in a smaller contraction of the solvent.

Another interesting fact to which the attention may now be drawn is that the difference in the ϕ° values of two successive members of the R_4NI series i.e., [$\phi^\circ(\text{R}_{n+1})_4\text{NI}$ $\phi^\circ(\text{RN})_4\text{NI}$] in solvents considered for the present communication is around 70 ml/mole and is almost independent of temperature. Further, this difference, i.e., 70 ml/mole very

Fig. 2. The temperature dependence of ϕ° of Pr_4NI in some hydrogen bonded solvents.

Fig. 3. The temperature dependence of ϕ° of Hep_4NI in some non-hydrogen bonded solvents.

Fig. 4. The temperature dependence of ϕ° of Hep_4NI in some hydrogen bonded solvents.

nearly corresponds to the difference in intrinsic volumes of the two successive R_4N^+ ions obtained from the relation $4/3\pi r^3 N$, r being the radius of the ion in question as given by Robinson and Stokes⁹. This observation suggests that the electrostriction in presence of the R_4N^+ ions is very little in these solvents and also that the addition of one CH_2 group to R-chain of the R_4N^+ ions, increases the volume of the ion by about 70 ml per mole. But since in many cases, the density could be measured only within a very limited range of concentrations due to solubility restrictions, it would be safer not to make any quantitative deductions. However, since the results indicate that R_4N^+ -solvent interaction is very slight, one wonders whether the variation of ϕ° with temperature, in the case of larger R_4N -iodides is only governed by I^- -solvent interaction alone. It is hoped that studies on apparent molal volumes in dilute solutions would throw more light on the behaviour of R_4N^+ ions in nonaqueous solvents.

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